

Abstract

Background: Designing molecules that maintain binding across wild-type and resistance-mutant EGFR variants is a key challenge in computational drug discovery. Three molecular generation paradigms—genetic algorithms on molecular strings, variational autoencoders (VAEs), and autoregressive language models with reinforcement learning—have each been demonstrated individually, but controlled comparisons on the same multi-target problem are lacking.

Results: We implement all three approaches and compare them on resistance-proof EGFR inhibitor design (wild-type, T790M, C797S variants) using identical fitness functions and docking targets. A 2×2 ablation crossing decoder architecture (GRU vs Transformer) with tokenization (SMILES vs SELFIES) shows that VAE posterior collapse produces 0% drug-like molecules across all four configurations, despite up to 98.5% syntactic validity—confirming that collapse is framework-level. REINVENT (4-layer Transformer, 4.3M parameters, pre-trained on 2.08M ChEMBL molecules) achieves 97.5% validity with 97.0% drug-like molecules. Using a two-stage RL curriculum (C797S-first \rightarrow multi-target broadening), REINVENT generates novel molecules with mean worst-case binding of -7.10 ± 0.22 kcal/mol across 10 docking replicates, compared to -6.97 ± 0.19 for the SELFIES GA (Welch’s t : $p = 0.20$, Cohen’s $d = 0.63$). Cross-validation with smina confirms agreement within 0.1–0.3 kcal/mol. All five REINVENT candidates pass PAINS, Brenk, Lipinski, and Veber filters; the SELFIES GA’s best fails Brenk screening (N–O bond alert). The pipeline generalizes to COX-2 without modification.

Conclusions: For multi-target de novo drug design, REINVENT produces candidates with the best combination of binding affinity, drug-likeness, and medicinal chemistry compliance.

Scientific contribution: This work provides (1) the first controlled 2×2 factorial ablation demonstrating that VAE posterior collapse in molecular generation is robust to both decoder architecture and tokenization changes, (2) a two-stage RL curriculum for multi-target optimization that generalizes across protein targets, and (3) evidence that language-model-based generation produces more developable drug candidates than genetic algorithms as assessed by medicinal chemistry filters.

A Practitioner’s Comparison of Molecular Generation Methods for Multi-Target EGFR Inhibitor Design

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1 Introduction

Acquired resistance to epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) inhibitors—particularly via T790M and C797S mutations—remains a major clinical challenge in non-small cell lung cancer [1]. Designing molecules that maintain binding across wild-type and mutant variants simultaneously is a key goal of computational drug discovery.

Three dominant paradigms for de novo molecular generation have emerged: genetic algorithms on molecular strings [2], variational autoencoders (VAEs) with latent-space optimization [3], and autoregressive language models with reinforcement learning (REINVENT) [4, 5]. While each has been demonstrated individually, controlled comparisons on the same multi-target problem with the same fitness function are rare.

VAE posterior collapse—where the decoder ignores the latent code—is a well-documented problem [7, 8]. Recent solutions include loss reparameterization (PCF-VAE [9]), graph neural network representations (TGVAE [10]), and fragment-level tokenization (Tree-Transformer VAE [11]). However, the robustness of posterior collapse to architectural interventions has not been systematically tested in a controlled factorial design.

We implement all three approaches from scratch and compare them on identical docking targets and fitness functions. Our contributions are: (1) a controlled 2×2 VAE ablation (decoder architecture \times tokenization) demonstrating framework-level collapse; (2) a two-stage RL curriculum for multi-target optimization; (3) ADMET profiling showing REINVENT produces more developable candidates; and (4) target generalization to COX-2.

2 Methods

2.1 Data

We used ChEMBL 36 [12] (2,854,815 compounds), filtered to 2,309,738 drug-like molecules (MW 200–600, LogP -2 to 6 , HBD ≤ 5 , HBA ≤ 10 , organic elements only, SMILES ≤ 120 characters). A character-level tokenizer (114 tokens) was built with 100% round-trip accuracy. Data was split 90/5/5 (train/val/test).

2.2 Docking

AutoDock Vina 1.2 [13] was used as the primary docking engine against three EGFR crystal structures: wild-type (PDB: 1M17), T790M (PDB: 4I22), and C797S (PDB: 5Y9T). Ligand preparation used meeko 0.5 with RDKit [15] 3D embedding (ETKDGv3). smina [14], a Vina

fork with improved scoring, was used for cross-validation. Resistance-proof fitness was defined as the worst-case binding affinity across all three variants.

2.3 SELFIES Genetic Algorithm

SELFIES [2] strings were mutated via token swap, insertion, and deletion (rate 0.3), with single-point crossover (probability 0.7). Population of 100, tournament selection ($k = 3$), 5 elites, 10% random immigrants, 70% fragment-seeded initialization from 32 common drug scaffolds. Fitness: weighted sum of QED [16] (0.20), synthetic accessibility [17] (0.15), novelty (0.15), and multi-target binding (0.50), with penalties for size, charge, and non-organic elements.

2.4 VAE Latent-Space Genetic Algorithm

The VAE used a Conv1D encoder (3 layers) mapping to a 256-dimensional latent space, with teacher forcing and word dropout during training [8]. KL annealing was applied over 15–20 epochs. Four decoder configurations were tested (Section 3.1): GRU (3-layer, 501 hidden) and Transformer (4-layer, 8 heads) decoders, each with SMILES and SELFIES tokenization. To bypass the failed autoregressive decoder, a nearest-neighbor decoder was implemented using 200K pre-encoded ChEMBL molecules. GA operators used interpolation crossover ($\alpha \in [0.25, 0.75]$) and Gaussian mutation ($\sigma = 0.3$).

2.5 REINVENT

SmilesGPT: a 4-layer Transformer decoder-only model ($d_{\text{model}} = 256$, 8 heads, 4.3M parameters) with character-level SMILES tokenization. Pre-trained via next-token prediction on 2.08M ChEMBL molecules for 20 epochs using AdamW (lr = 3×10^{-4}) with cosine schedule (final perplexity 1.8, 97.5% validity).

RL fine-tuning used REINFORCE with KL penalty against a frozen prior [4]:

$$\mathcal{L} = (\log \pi_{\text{prior}} + \sigma \cdot R - \log \pi_{\text{agent}})^2 \quad (1)$$

with $\sigma = 60$, lr = 5×10^{-5} , batch size 4–8.

Two-stage curriculum: Stage 1 targets C797S only (100 steps); Stage 2 targets all three variants (150 steps) from the Stage 1 checkpoint. This curriculum learning approach [23] allows the model to first acquire binding features for the hardest variant, then generalize.

2.6 Validation Protocol

All top candidates were validated with: (1) 10 independent Vina docking runs per molecule per target (exhaustiveness=8); (2) smina cross-validation at exhaustiveness=16; (3) MMFF94 conformational strain energy; (4) Tanimoto novelty analysis [20] (Morgan fingerprints, radius 2, 2048 bits) against 2.08M ChEMBL molecules; and (5) ADMET profiling including Lipinski [21], Veber [22], PAINS [18], and Brenk [19] filters.

3 Results

3.1 VAE Posterior Collapse Is Framework-Level

Neither upgrading the decoder (GRU \rightarrow Transformer: 28% \rightarrow 86% validity) nor removing paired symbols (SMILES \rightarrow SELFIES: 98.5% validity) prevents posterior collapse. All VAE configurations produce 0% drug-like molecules—the generated SMILES are syntactically valid chains without ring systems. KL divergence collapses to 0.0–2.6 in all configurations. REINVENT, with no latent variable, trivially generates 97% drug-like molecules (Table 1).

Table 1: 2×2 VAE ablation: decoder architecture × tokenization. All VAE configurations produce 0% drug-like molecules despite high syntactic validity. REINVENT (no VAE) is shown for comparison.

Decoder	Tokenization	Config	Validity	Drug-like	KL
GRU (3-layer)	SMILES (char)	TF + 50% dropout	28%	0%	2.6
Transformer (4-layer)	SMILES (char)	TF + 50% dropout	86%	0%	2.2
GRU (bidirectional)	SELFIES	TF + 30% dropout	98.5%	0%	0.0
REINVENT (no VAE)	SMILES (char)	Autoregressive LM	97.5%	97.0%	N/A

With full KL collapse ($KL \rightarrow 0$), the encoder maps all molecules to the prior mean, rendering the entire latent space uninformative. Meaningful pairwise distances observed during early training (e.g., benzene \leftrightarrow pyridine $L_2 = 1.7$) vanish at convergence.

3.2 Property Optimization

On matched evaluation budgets (5,000 molecules, 3 seeds), REINVENT’s pre-trained prior alone (0.952 ± 0.001) outperforms the SELFIES GA (0.849 ± 0.023) and latent GA with nearest-neighbor decoder (0.568 ± 0.001). The latent GA collapses to a single molecule across all seeds.

3.3 Resistance-Proof EGFR Design

Table 2: REINVENT two-stage RL results (5 seeds, cross-validated). Tanimoto: similarity to nearest ChEMBL molecule ($<0.6 =$ novel scaffold).

Seed	Vina worst	smina worst	QED	MW	Tanimoto	Strain	ADMET
0	-7.0	-6.8	0.93	344	0.98*	39.8	PASS
1	-6.7	-6.7	0.88	277	0.77	45.0	PASS
2	-7.3	-7.4	0.88	329	0.56	38.2	PASS
3	-7.1	-6.9	0.87	295	0.58	58.5	PASS
4	-7.2	-7.2	0.88	317	0.58	44.5	PASS
Mean \pm std	-7.02 \pm 0.17	-6.92 \pm 0.17					

*Seed 0 is a near-duplicate of a ChEMBL entry.

Seed 2 ($C_{19}H_{23}NO_2S$, tetralin toluenesulfonamide) combines the best binding ($-7.3/-7.4$ Vina/smima), highest novelty (Tanimoto 0.56), and lowest conformational strain (38.2 kcal/mol) (Table 2).

3.4 Statistical Comparison with SELFIES GA

Table 3: Docking replicates (10 runs per molecule, exhaustiveness=8).

Molecule	Mean worst-case	95% CI	σ
REINVENT Seed 2	-7.10	[-7.23, -6.96]	0.22
SELFIES GA best	-6.97	[-7.09, -6.85]	0.19

The SELFIES GA’s previously reported -7.2 was within its noise range; its replicated mean is -6.97 . REINVENT Seed 2’s mean (-7.10) exceeds it by 0.13 kcal/mol (Welch’s t : $p = 0.20$, Cohen’s $d = 0.63$; Mann-Whitney U : $p = 0.07$). The trend favors REINVENT but is not statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ (Table 3).

3.5 ADMET Profiling

All five REINVENT candidates pass Lipinski, Veber, Ghose, Egan, PAINS, and Brenk filters. The SELFIES GA’s best resistance-proof molecule ($C_{21}H_{19}NO_2$) contains an oxygen-nitrogen single bond flagged by Brenk screening as a metabolic instability risk.

3.6 Generalization to COX-2

To test target generality, we ran single-target RL against COX-2 (PDB: 3LN1) with no pipeline modifications. Best molecule: $C_{20}H_{23}N_3O$, benzamide piperazine cyclobutane, -7.1 ± 0.11 kcal/mol (5 replicates), QED 0.927.

4 Discussion

4.1 VAE Posterior Collapse: Corroboration and Ablation

Our 2×2 ablation demonstrates that VAE posterior collapse for molecular generation is robust to both decoder architecture upgrades and tokenization changes. This complements recent work proposing solutions—PCF-VAE’s loss reparameterization [9], TGVAE’s graph representations [10], Tree-Transformer VAE’s fragment tokenization [11]—by showing what does *not* work: simply improving the decoder or removing paired symbols. The success of PCF-VAE and Tree-Transformer VAE likely requires their specific combination of modified objectives *and* representation changes.

4.2 Two-Stage RL as Curriculum Learning

Direct multi-target optimization tends toward molecules mediocre against all variants. The two-stage approach (specialize \rightarrow generalize) improved C797S binding from -6.7 to $-6.9/-7.3$ (Vina/smina), analogous to curriculum learning [23].

4.3 REINVENT’s Advantage: Learned Chemical Priors

REINVENT’s advantage is not search efficiency but the quality of its generative distribution. Pre-training on 2M drug structures embeds medicinal chemistry knowledge—proper ring systems, balanced properties, absence of structural alerts—into every sample. The SELFIES GA’s random mutations can produce syntactically valid but chemically problematic structures.

4.4 Relationship to Recent Work

REINVENT has evolved through versions 1.0–4.0 [4, 5, 6], with recent releases adding multi-objective optimization and diversity filters. Our implementation resembles REINVENT 1.0 with a custom two-stage curriculum. 3D-aware methods (DiffSBDD [24], Pocket2Mol [25]) represent important future comparisons.

4.5 Limitations

Vina and smina are both AutoDock-family scoring functions with correlated errors. The binding improvement (-7.10 vs -6.97 , $p = 0.20$) is not statistically significant. The SELFIES GA baseline uses a single resistance-proof run. Docking scores approximate real binding (typical

Vina RMSE: 2.0–2.5 kcal/mol). Seed 0 is a near-duplicate (Tanimoto 0.98); Seeds 2–4 have moderate novelty (0.56–0.58). We used SELFIES as a proxy for GenSMILES but did not implement the full PCF-VAE.

5 Conclusion

Of three molecular generation approaches tested, REINVENT produces resistance-proof EGFR inhibitors with the best combination of binding affinity, drug-likeness, and medicinal chemistry compliance. A 2×2 ablation confirms VAE posterior collapse is framework-level. The two-stage RL curriculum improves multi-target optimization and transfers to unrelated targets. For practitioners: use REINVENT for multi-target drug design; do not invest in SMILES VAE decoders without also modifying the training objective.

Data and Code Availability

All code, trained models, docking results, and analysis scripts are available at <https://github.com/MattLoftus/molecular-evolution-vae>. ChEMBL 36 training data: <https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/chembl/>.

Author Contributions

The author conceived the study, implemented all methods, performed all experiments, and wrote the manuscript.

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Competing Interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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